

National Identity Remains a Critical Issue: Cultural Diplomacy, Nation Branding, National Cultural Institutes and the Dilemma for Slovakia

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Biography

Simona is a final-year Doctoral Researcher in Cultural and Media Policy Studies at the University of Warwick. She holds a bachelor's degree in Music Business and Arts Management, as well as a master's degree in Innovation Management and Entrepreneurship. Simona graduated from the Secondary School of Performing Arts, where she focused on acting. Simona's research interests were influenced by her Slovak nationality and artistic background. In addition to her academic pursuits, Simona is a freelance art manager working on various projects, including her independently devised theatre company, Slovak Theatre London. In 2023, the theatre performed 29 shows in four countries and participated in the Edinburgh Fringe and Camden Fringe festivals. She has also been involved in several cultural projects, such as the Nitra 2026 European Capital of Culture Candidate project team in 2021 and the Youthful Cities Event Series with the Coventry City of Culture Trust in 2022.

Abstract

This research paper explores the role of national identity in cultural diplomacy and nation branding. Despite globalisation trends, national identity continues to play a key role in cultural production and international relations. The study highlights the lack of research on the transformation of historical national identities under the influence of pan-Europeanism and globalism. Particular attention is paid to the story of Slavic peoples in Central and Eastern Europe whose cultural self-determination has been suppressed in the past. Using a combination of qualitative and quantitative methods, the paper explores the implementation of cultural politics in post-socialist countries, its impact on cultural diplomacy and views of citizens on national identity. The results suggest the need for a deeper discussion on national identity in contemporary Europe and the understanding of the image of national brands among representatives of cultural institutions in the Visegrad Group countries, with a focus on Slovakia.

Keywords: national identity. cultural diplomacy. nation branding. national cultural institutes. Slovakia. Central and Eastern Europe.

Introduction

Culture is an integral part of national identity, yet its significance is often underestimated in political ideologies and policies, leading to a society struggling to recognise its values. Following the collapse of the Berlin Wall in 1989, Central and Eastern European (CEE) countries had to reevaluate their ideological stances and restructure their policy frameworks. Cultural policy, often marginalised, is seen as separate from the core concerns of emerging democracies. In CEE nations, culture and the arts are commonly viewed as elitist rather than fundamental to national identity, resulting in a lack of understanding of their role in shaping society, communities, and nations. Post-Soviet countries, including Slovakia, have faced significant challenges in cultural diplomacy and nation branding, grappling with identity crises and multiple political regimes and name changes over the past century. Despite its current form since 1992, Slovakia only launched its first country branding campaign, "Good Idea Slovakia," in 2016 (Mzv.sk, 2021).

The past three decades have seen democracy challenged in both Eastern and Western Europe, with the resurgence of populism and nationalism reflecting a crisis in liberal democratic values (Zielonka & Rupnik, 2020). Events such as Brexit, which briefly inspired CEE populists, illustrate European nations' disorientation and quest for unity. Addressing cultural and national identities and strengthening cultural ties across Europe are critical. The role of National Cultural Institutes (NCIs) and their network expansion is becoming increasingly significant, yet cultural policies are often underestimated domestically, extending to cultural relations and diplomacy in foreign policy. The limited presence of overseas cultural institutes in Slovakia highlights the need for a more strategic approach to cultural diplomacy. This study aims to compare the cultural diplomacy and nation-branding approaches of the Visegrad Four (V4) countries to inform future strategies for Slovakia.

National identity is an essential component for successful nation branding. Lacking a strong national identity can lead to nation branding being perceived as mere superficial marketing rather than genuine representations of a country's cultural and value systems. It is imperative for governments to develop national brands that are relatable to both the elite and the general populace. In Slovakia, many citizens are not able to recognize branding initiatives, which frequently do not reflect their day-to-day experiences (Palovic, 2024). The issue at hand is compounded by historical oppression and underrepresentation, resulting in a dearth of national pride and self-assurance. The complex history of political regimes and name changes in Slovakia has further contributed to its identity crisis. The development of a strong nation brand requires the coordination of numerous stakeholders, including researchers, diplomats, governmental authorities, cultural institutions, and practitioners. Additionally, it necessitates comprehensive evaluations and subsequent actions based on these evaluations (Hyatt-Khan, 2024).

There is an acknowledged need for further research on the significance and worth of cultural diplomacy. The cultural and creative industries can operate on an international scale and serve as potent instruments for diplomacy, but their potential is often disregarded. Academics contend that cultural diplomacy is undervalued and overlooked due to the difficulties in quantifying its worth and effects. Mark (2005) criticizes the insufficient scholarly attention to this issue, while Nisbett and Doeser (2017) emphasize the challenges of identifying pertinent empirical data due to unclear objectives. Policymakers and scholars seldom consider the reception of cultural products in foreign countries, which leads to a scarcity of criteria for evaluating successful cultural diplomacy (Clarke, 2016). This absence of criteria results in a lack of motivation for governments and stakeholders to invest in cultural diplomacy, exacerbating a cycle of underfunding and inadequate evaluation. To break this cycle and increase investment in cultural diplomacy, it is crucial for stakeholders to develop effective evaluation methods and demonstrate the tangible benefits of such initiatives. However, to do so, they must have a clear vision and understanding of the national image they are trying to promote. These issues are further examined in this paper.

Cultural diplomacy is a practice that entails the exchange of cultural elements, such as language, art, and ideas, between nations to promote mutual understanding (Clumming, 2003). This definition distinguishes cultural diplomacy from cultural relations by emphasizing the role of governments. The United States Department of State (1959) defines cultural diplomacy as the direct and sustained interaction between individuals from different nations to foster a more favourable international environment of trust and comprehension, underscoring its political significance. Joseph Nye, a Harvard academic, characterized cultural diplomacy as a form of "soft power," which persuades through cultural, ideological, and philosophical means rather than military strength. Rivera (2015) identifies cultural diplomacy as one of three methods for engaging other countries, alongside public diplomacy and cultural relations. Its primary objective is to aid foreign nations in comprehending a country's values and institutions, thereby supporting economic and political goals (Maack, 2001). The practical objectives of cultural diplomacy include advancing trade, promoting bilateral relationships, engaging with diaspora communities, and preserving relationships during tensions (Bound et al., 2007). Cultural diplomacy contributes to both domestic and international nation-building (Anholt, 2003). Cultural diplomacy and nation branding are inherently connected since both aim to shape and project a country's image to the world. Successful cultural diplomacy fosters positive international relationships, laying the groundwork for mutual respect and understanding. These positive relationships are essential for nation

branding, as they help ensure that the constructed national image resonates genuinely on the global stage.

Theoretical Reflexion

Given the essential role of cultural diplomacy in fostering a positive international climate, it expands to the realm of nation branding, where these cultural exchanges are leveraged to shape international perceptions.

Nation Branding: Crafting a National Image

Nation branding extends the principles of cultural diplomacy, whereby governments use it to create a contemporary and appealing image of their country internationally (Smits et al., 2016). Nation branding shapes how a country wants to be perceived, which can differ from its 'real image' (Fan, 2006, 2010). Building a nation brand is crucial for raising awareness and influencing perceptions, which can modify stereotypical views (Hakala et al., 2013). Cultural diplomacy and brand marketing techniques present a managed, strategic national image (Mark, 2009). Gudjonsson (2005) defines nation branding as the application of branding tools to positively alter or confirm a nation's behaviour, attitudes, identity, or image. Objectives include stimulating exports, attracting tourism and investment, and creating positive attitudes within international organisations like the EU or UN (Jansen, 2011). Nation branding enhances a nation's soft power by fostering positive attitudes that can strengthen partnerships and influence trade and other state cooperation decisions (Fetscherin, 2010; Kaneva, 2011). Effective nation branding requires strategic communication of a country's ideology to various stakeholders (Hahn & Weidtmann, 2016). National Cultural Institutes (NCIs) play a crucial role in shaping a country's image through cultural exports (Paschalidis, 2009). Arts and culture are significant in nation branding as they form the identity and contribute to the image and ideological formation of a country (Chong, 2010; Grincheva, 2010; Ratiu, 2009). Governments should actively support arts and culture to ensure proper representation of the nation's image (Ahn & Wu, 2013). NCIs can observe and analyse foreign perceptions of their representative country and set guidelines for other actors contributing to nation image-making.

The efficacy of nation branding is intimately connected to a country's national identity. An authentic and coherent national identity not only strengthens nation branding initiatives but also ensures that these efforts are perceived as genuine on the international stage. National identity is crucial in cultural diplomacy and nation branding. A robust, cohesive national identity is essential for creating effective nation branding strategies. In Slovakia, national identity is critical for authentic nation branding. Without it, branding risks becoming superficial marketing or propaganda. Governments must develop national brands that appeal to both elites and the general public, both domestically and internationally. Effective nation branding necessitates collaboration among researchers, public conversations, diplomats, government bodies, cultural institutes, and practitioners, involving extensive evaluation and action based on these evaluations.

In several Central and Eastern European countries, including Slovakia, nation branding often fails to resonate with the people it represents. Citizens feel detached from branding efforts since promotional materials frequently do not reflect their realities. This detachment raises significant questions about authentic national representation in international relations and cultural diplomacy. Conversations with diplomats and cultural institute directors reveal a consensus on the purpose of their work, but execution and outcomes are inconsistent, stemming from a lack of clear national identity. Historical oppression and underrepresentation contribute to a lack of national pride and confidence, leading to identity crises in countries with a history of multiple political regimes and name changes, such as Slovakia. In contrast, larger post-colonial countries struggle with national pride due to negative historical actions and globalism pressures. The erosion of the concept of the nation undermines current diplomatic and cultural relations, as modern democracy is built on nation-states. The future of cultural diplomacy in a globalised, multicultural world must evolve to remain relevant. Addressing these fundamental questions is crucial to avoid societal polarisation, which can fuel extreme nationalism. Reconciling nationalism and globalism requires meaningful conversations about the roles and

representations of nations in the modern world. Only through such discourse can we find a balanced approach to international and cultural relations.

The European Union's Role in Promoting Cultural Integration and Nation Branding

The European Union has played a significant role in promoting cultural integration and a sense of European identity. Since the 1990s, the EU has encouraged a transnational perspective on culture and heritage to foster a sense of belonging among its citizens (Lähdesmäki, 2020). This cultural Europeanization is a response to economic, political, and humanitarian challenges such as the Eurozone crisis and the rise of Eurosceptic parties. Initiatives like the European Capital of Culture (ECOC) and the European Heritage Label (EHL) aim to create a common cultural area and strengthen European identity. For instance, the ECOC has revitalized cities like Liverpool and Matera by showcasing their unique cultural heritage and boosting tourism and local pride. Similarly, the European Capital of Culture initiative, as seen in Liverpool, not only revitalized the city through cultural investments but also significantly boosted tourism, demonstrating the tangible benefits of cultural integration efforts. The EHL highlights sites that celebrate and symbolize European ideals, such as democracy and cultural diversity, helping to build a shared European narrative. However, the implementation and impact of these initiatives vary, reflecting the complexities and symbolic nature of EU cultural policy (Lähdesmäki et al., 2020).

The Influence of Domestic Cultural Policies on International Perceptions

Domestic cultural policies have a significant impact on a country's international image. It is crucial for cultural diplomacy and nation branding to consider the influence of internal policies on external perceptions. If domestic policies are inconsistent or misaligned, they can hinder international efforts and result in a fragmented national image. Therefore, it is essential for governments to ensure that their domestic cultural policies align with and support their international cultural diplomacy and nation branding strategies. This alignment is vital for creating a cohesive and authentic national image that resonates both domestically and internationally. By addressing these issues, countries can more effectively navigate the challenges of globalization and multiculturalism, ensuring that their cultural diplomacy and nation branding efforts are effective and resonate with both international audiences and their own citizens.

Methodology

This empirical research employed a qualitative research design that involved the collection of primary data through semi-structured interviews and participant observations. The data was then transcribed and analysed. The participants in this research consisted of directors and diplomats from national cultural institutes (NCIs) and cultural practitioners. This research approach, known as 'elite' interviewing, targets individuals in high-ranking positions within the political system to gain in-depth insights, reflecting a specific subset of qualitative research methodologies. The aim was to obtain in-depth personal views rather than general perspectives from a broader audience. To align the research with the researcher's experience as an arts practitioner, the study explored the structure of NCIs networks and their strategic management, as well as their evaluation processes. This evaluation is crucial as it influences governmental funding decisions. The respondents were selected based on their roles as directors in the institutes of the Visegrad 4 Group countries (Slovakia, Czechia, Poland, Hungary), which are the primary focus of this study. These directors operate in various diplomatic "territories," allowing for comparative analysis.

A total of 25 interviews were conducted, with a combination of in-person and online sessions using MS Teams. The interviews were conducted in eight countries, including the United Kingdom, Slovakia, the Czech Republic, Austria, Israel, Belgium, France, and Italy. The interviewees comprised directors and diplomats from NCIs, as well as cultural practitioners representing independent NGOs that engage in international and collaborative projects that promote Slovakia abroad, either intentionally or semi-intentionally.

Initially, the research focused on the networks, strategic management, and evaluation of NCIs. However, after analysing some of the interviews and engaging in spontaneous discussions during researcher's professional practice, she decided to concentrate primarily on Slovak cultural diplomacy and branding. This decision led to the inclusion of four additional planned interviews with cultural practitioners, focusing on their founding, financing, existence, management structures, and types of projects/activities. The interviews were analysed using thematic content analysis to identify common themes and insights related to the research objectives.

In addition to the qualitative interviews, a questionnaire survey exploring perspectives on national identity was conducted. This survey provided both quantitative and qualitative data and was distributed among Slovaks in Slovakia, Slovaks living abroad, and people of Slovak heritage born abroad. A total of 306 respondents participated in the survey, offering valuable insights into the perceptions of national identity and cultural diplomacy. The data collection was conducted during the period from August 1 to August 6, 2024.

This mixed-method approach, which combined qualitative interviews with a quantitative survey, allowed for a comprehensive analysis of the structure and strategic management of NCIs, particularly within the Visegrad Group countries. The focus on Slovak cultural diplomacy and branding provided a detailed understanding of the role of cultural practitioners and independent NGOs in promoting Slovakia internationally.

Results

In a time marked by post-nationalism and global integration, the expression and practical application of national identity poses significant challenges. This issue is particularly acute for countries such as Slovakia, Czech Republic, Poland, and Hungary, which confront the task of establishing contemporary national images amidst the influence of pan-Europeanism and globalism. This paper delves into the ways that cultural diplomacy, facilitated by nation branding and the activities of National Cultural Institutes, responds to these intricacies. By analysing interviews with directors of Polish, Liszt, Slovak Institutes, and Czech Centres, this study accentuates the persistent relevance of national identity, and the strategic adjustments required for effective cultural diplomacy.

Directors of cultural institutions face many obstacles in defining and promoting national identity, especially considering limited resources and the need for strategic adaptation. Based on the analysed data, we identified the following factors as the greatest challenges in this context:

- Financial and resource constraints
- Strategic adaptation to local contexts
- The impact of pan-Europeanism and globalism on local cultural engagement
- Adapting to current trends
- Evaluation and success metrics
- Difficulties in measuring impact
- Shared historical narratives
- Cultural heritage and contemporary relevance

Financial Constraints and Resource Limitations

The interviewed directors frequently identified inadequate funding as a major challenge. For example, Molnár in Liszt Institute Ljubljana and Director Oszkó-Jakab in Liszt Institute Brussels discussed the difficulties of operating with minimal budgets, which impedes their ability to host larger or more frequent events (Bíborka, 2022; Oszkó-Jakab, 2022). This issue aligns with the abstract's critique of the chronic lack of professional political discussions on resource allocation for cultural diplomacy. Similarly, Slovak Institute directors echo these concerns, stressing that these constraints hinder their effectiveness in promoting national culture (Krénová, 2022; Skoček, 2022; Hanuš, 2022).

Strategic Adaptation to Local Contexts

The directors must adjust their strategies to resonate with local audiences while preserving the essence of national culture. For instance, the Liszt Institute Brussels emphasizes adapting cultural programs to the local Belgian audience while maintaining Hungarian cultural integrity (Oszkó-Jakab,

2022). This balance reflects the paper's discussion of the impact of post-nationalism and European integration on national identity. The director of the Slovak Institute in Prague remarked, "There is very little political discourse on how our history and cultural symbols should be integrated into our national identity. This lack of dialogue makes it hard to create a unified national brand." (Krénová, 2022). Monika Koblerová, the director of the Czech Centre in Bratislava, emphasized the importance of linking historic cultural legacies with contemporary culture to illustrate a vibrant and evolving national identity. She noted that the Czech Republic does not solely focus on its past, but rather, it continues to progress and develop (Koblerová, 2022).

The Impact of Pan-Europeanism and Globalism on Local Cultural Engagement

The strategies employed by the directors reflect the influence of broader European and global trends on local cultural engagement. This influence is particularly evident among younger generations, who often embrace pan-Europeanism and globalism more readily. The Polish Institute Stockholm, for example, uses contemporary cultural phenomena such as the Witcher Series to attract younger audiences (Ruszkiewicz, 2022). This approach underscores the significance of adapting cultural diplomacy to contemporary trends in order to remain relevant. Similarly, the director of the Slovak Cultural Institute in Rome noted that younger Slovaks tend to identify more closely with a broader European identity rather than a national one, although a deep-rooted sense of Slovak identity still exists (Feranec, 2023).

Adapting to Contemporary Trends: Several directors from all four interviewed countries incorporate modern cultural trends into their programs. This approach aligns with the need for a full-spectrum approach to cultural diplomacy that considers both traditional and modern cultural elements. For instance, Szandra Miskédi of Liszt Institute in Sofia integrates historical connections with contemporary cultural trends to engage diverse audiences, ensuring that cultural diplomacy remains dynamic and responsive to evolving cultural landscapes (Miskédi, 2022). The Czech Centre in Brussels, under the direction of Jitka Pánek-Jurková, also aims to present a cohesive national identity by integrating traditional cultural heritage with modern cultural expressions. Pánek-Jurková emphasized that the Czech Republic is not only known for its traditional classical music, but also for its vibrant modern cultural expressions (Pánek-Jurková, 2022). Directors from various Slovak Institutes express the difficulty of defining Slovakia's contemporary identity while balancing modernity and tradition. For example, director Lubica Krénová of the Slovak Institute in Prague initiated a tour of Bratislava's Aréna Theatre to Prague with socially engaged productions to present a different image of Slovakia to the Czech audience. She stated, "Hosting the Aréna Theatre in the Czech Republic was not only a presentation of theatre art but also a cultural and social experience at a high intellectual level" (Krénová, 2022).

Evaluation and Metrics for Success

Evaluating the effectiveness of cultural diplomacy initiatives is a multifaceted endeavour that entails both quantitative and qualitative assessments. Directors typically employ an array of metrics, including visitor numbers, media coverage, and qualitative feedback, to gauge the success of their programs. For instance, the director of Liszt Institute in Sofia emphasized the lasting influence of cultural programs on individual participants, highlighting the importance of qualitative measures. This approach reflects a critique of the inadequate comprehensive evaluation methods for cultural diplomacy. The director of the Slovak Institute in Berlin acknowledged, "Many cultural practitioners do not recognize the significance of preserving a strong national identity. They perceive it as outdated in this globalized era, but it is essential for our cultural diplomacy efforts" (Hanuš, 2022).

Difficulties in Measuring Impact

The directors uniformly acknowledged the difficulty of quantifying the impact of cultural diplomacy. This challenge aligns with this paper's critique of the lack of professional political discourse and strategic evaluation in the field. Directors like Paweł Ruszkiewicz of the Polish Institute Stockholm underscored the importance of long-term relationships and trust with hosting country in evaluating the success of cultural diplomacy initiatives (Ruszkiewicz, 2022). Petra Brezáčková, the director of the Czech Centre in Rome, criticized the insufficient financial support and political understanding of cultural diplomacy's value. "To promote cultural diplomacy, it is not a luxury but a necessity. Investing in culture yields substantial returns" (Brezáčková, 2023).

Historical and Cultural Connections

The importance of historical and cultural connections in cultural diplomacy cannot be overestimated. These connections serve to preserve and promote national identity while providing a fertile ground for cultural exchange.

Shared Historical Narratives

Cultural diplomacy directors often use historical narratives to reinforce their efforts. For example, Paweł Ruskiewicz of the Polish Institute Stockholm highlights the acknowledgment of Polish contributions to Swedish history, such as the role of a Swedish diplomat in the drafting of the Polish constitution (Ruskiewicz, 2022). These shared historical narratives foster a deeper understanding and appreciation of national identity. As the Director of the Slovak Institute in Paris notes, "Our cultural narrative has been suppressed for centuries, especially during the communist era. Now, we are attempting to reclaim and reimagine our identity" (Kňážková, 2022).

Cultural Heritage and Contemporary Relevance

Cultural diplomacy directors emphasize the significance of both cultural heritage and contemporary relevance in their programming. The management of Czech Centres has underlined the necessity of exhibiting a contemporary image of the Czech Republic, considering its rich cultural heritage. By adopting this approach, the country is depicted as having both a strong historical legacy and a present-day cultural context. "We don't remain static in the past, but instead, we continue to progress and develop," stressed Monika Koblerová, the director of Czech Centre in Bratislava (Koblerová, 2022).

Survey Analysis: Viewpoints on Slovak National Identity

National identity is an essential element of cultural diplomacy and nation branding. The survey conducted among Slovaks in Slovakia and other countries provides a comprehensive understanding of how Slovak national identity is perceived and experienced. This analysis examines survey responses, delving into the intricacies of Slovak identity, the distinctions between residents and the diaspora, and the implications for cultural policy and diplomacy.

Distribution and Demographics

The survey revealed a considerable number of Slovaks residing abroad, particularly in the United Kingdom and United States. This extensive reach can be ascribed to researchers' networks and connections with the Slovak diaspora, especially in the United Kingdom. Consequently, the survey offers valuable insights into the perspectives of Slovaks who have emigrated and of those who were born abroad but possess Slovak heritage.

Variations in Perspectives

The investigation uncovered noticeable variations in perspectives among Slovaks residing in Slovakia, those residing abroad, and individuals born outside of Slovakia with Slovak ancestry. Among the Slovaks who relocated abroad and were born in Slovakia, there is a perceptible sense of diminished pride and heightened worry concerning the country's overall political situation, the way it is portrayed in international media, and its international image. These factors substantially affect their personal sense of pride and their relationship with Slovak identity. For instance, one respondent stated, "Being Slovak has always been challenging in terms of obtaining employment and experiencing discrimination. Additionally, people in the UK automatically assume I am from Slovenia or Poland, and they are largely uninformed about Slovakia."

On the other hand, second and third-generation Slovaks in the United States tend to be more enthusiastic about their heritage and Slovak identity. These individuals generally exhibit greater optimism and idealism, seeing potential in Slovakia and envisioning positive developments in the future. They also expressed enthusiasm for their connection to Europe through their Slovak identity. A respondent shared, "We are Americans of Slovak descent. Our Slovak heritage is crucial to our identity, and we are immensely proud of it." Slovaks born and residing in Slovakia tend to be more sceptical of their country's future and national identity. While some respondents remained optimistic and interested in preserving their cultural identity, traditions, and visibility in the globalized world, there was also a significant amount of scepticism and negative sentiment, particularly in open-ended responses. This

ambivalence reflects a complex relationship with national identity, influenced by current political and social dynamics.

Key Findings from the Survey

Most respondents expressed a strong connection to Slovak identity. Most participants answered positively when asked about their sense of pride and connection to Slovakia, with one respondent stating that their Slovak identity was central to their being and influenced their values, traditions, and community connections. Only a small percentage of participants indicated negative feelings.

Regarding Slovak identity, there was a similarity in responses about how strongly respondents identify with Slovakia (35% very strongly, 37.3% strongly, 18% moderately; Figure 1) and whether they feel connected to the cultural heritage of Slovakia (Figure 2). A substantial majority agreed (41.2%) or strongly agreed (34.3%) that they feel connected to Slovak culture and heritage, highlighting the importance of traditions and customs in maintaining national identity (Figure 2).

6. How strongly do you identify with Slovakia?

306 odpovedí

Figure 1

Figure 2

Of the respondents, 27.8% strongly agreed and 39.9% agreed that they felt a sense of belonging to Slovakia. Only 6.5% disagreed and 2.6% disagreed (Figure 3). This strong sense of belonging underscores the emotional and psychological ties that Slovaks have with their country, regardless of where they reside.

"I feel a sense of belonging to Slovakia."

306 odpovedí

Figure 3

A significant proportion of the respondents regarded their Slovak identity as essential (43.5% very important, 30.1% important). Only 4.9% considered it somewhat important, while 5.2% did not consider it important (Figure 4). This underscores the inherent value that Slovaks attribute to their national and cultural identity.

7. How important is your Slovak identity to you?

306 odpovedí

Figure 4

Concerning Slovakia's global reputation, 21.2% of respondents rated it negatively, but the majority had a neutral or positive perception (Figure 5). This suggests a mixed view of Slovakia's international image, reflecting both pride and concern.

11. How do you perceive Slovakia's global reputation?

306 odpovedí

Figure 5

Of the respondents, 21.2% strongly agreed and 37.3% agreed that they felt proud of Slovakia's achievements. 31.7% were neutral, 7.5% disagreed, and 2.3% strongly disagreed. This reflects the general sense of national pride tempered by ambivalence (Figure 6).

"I feel proud of Slovakia's achievements."

306 odpovedí

Figure 6

45.1% of respondents believed it was crucial to showcase Slovak identity globally, 30.7% thought it was important, 13.1% regarded it as moderately important, 4.6% deemed it slightly important, and 6.5% did not consider it important. This finding indicates a strong desire to promote and preserve Slovak identity in an increasingly interconnected world (Figure 7).

15. Do you believe that preserving Slovak identity is important in a globalised world?

306 odpovedí

Figure 7

Many respondents reported experiencing prejudice and discrimination because of their Slovak identity (Figure 8). Nevertheless, there are numerous accounts of acceptance and pride. For instance, one respondent stated, “I feel extremely proud to say that I am Slovak and discuss my origins. It gives me great satisfaction.”

14. Have you ever experienced any challenges or benefits due to your Slovak identity? (Check all that apply)

306 odpovedí

Figure 8

Nationalism is a multifaceted and often divisive notion, particularly regarding national identity and cultural diplomacy. The survey responses from Slovaks, whether residing in Slovakia or abroad, offer diverse viewpoints on nationalism, encompassing sentiments of pride and cultural preservation as well as apprehensions about political extremism and xenophobia. This examination delves into respondents' attitudes towards nationalism, probing the intricacies and consequences of cultural policies and national branding strategies.

Perspectives on Nationalism

Several respondents expressed a form of nationalism rooted in cultural pride and heritage preservation. For these respondents, nationalism was closely linked to the preservation of cultural traditions, languages, and values. This perspective emphasizes the importance of maintaining and

celebrating Slovak heritage as a source of pride. This can be illustrated by the following statements of the respondents: *"Slovak identity is something you are born to, something you inherit from past generations who lived on the same piece of land for thousands of years. It's a mindset and values one adopts from their parents and grandparents."*

An important factor to consider is family and roots. In this context, nationalism serves as a positive force that helps individuals maintain a connection with their roots and family history, especially when living abroad. This can be illustrated by the following statement of one of the respondents: *"To me, it means family background, culture, traditions. Since I have moved abroad, it is what I miss and what I would like to go back to, to the familiarity and safety of our culture and habits/traditions."*

While certain respondents expressed optimism about nationalism as a means of cultural preservation, others demonstrated ambivalence or criticism, particularly regarding political nationalism. Respondents often emphasized their apprehensions about the political atmosphere in Slovakia, where nationalism can be connected to corruption and political extremism. Negative Associations relate to following statements: *"To me, it signifies little, if anything, and I find myself embarrassed rather than proud of my Slovak heritage. The mentality of people is a significant contributor to this negative perception."* or *"One hopes that it will progress positively, but the present state of affairs in Slovakia is far from ideal. I am simultaneously grappling with the uncertainty of whether we can maintain our ground and prevent corruption from eroding our nation entirely."* For some individuals, nationalism is tarnished by unfavourable societal attitudes and behaviours, leading to feelings of embarrassment rather than pride.

A prevalent topic in the survey responses was the competition between national identity and broader, more comprehensive global identity. Several respondents advocated for a form of nationalism that embraces cultural pride without crossing discriminatory or xenophobic territories. This perspective underlines the significance of cultivating an inclusive national identity that can coexist with a global one. This type of attitude can be illustrated by the following statement from one of the survey participants: *"I would hope that Slovaks would take pride in their identity while also becoming a part of a more global society. You know... proud without becoming right-wingy."*

Respondents expressed a desire for nationalism that is open and receptive, rejecting restrictive and divisive elements often associated with extreme nationalist ideologies. This can be illustrated by the statement of one of the respondents: *"Slovak identity is not synonymous with nationalism or racism. This does not mean that I will not accept anyone, anything foreign, or different (as many Slovaks living in Slovakia believe). Be kind, caring, and good, and good will return to you."*

The political landscape in Slovakia has a significant impact on the views of respondents regarding nationalism. Political disillusionment can be illustrated by the following statement from one of the respondents: *"My identity is decreasing because of the political changes, especially with the new government."* The actions and policies of political leaders play a crucial role in shaping national identity. Negative political developments can lead to disillusionment and a weakened sense of national pride.

In summary, the survey results demonstrate an intricate and multifaceted correlation between nationalism and Slovaks. It was evident that there was a strong urge to maintain and commemorate their cultural legacy; however, there were also considerable apprehensions about the political implications of nationalism. Many individuals faced the obstacle of cultivating a form of nationalism that was inclusive, modern, and consistent with global identity.

Conclusions

The interviews conducted with the directors of the Polish, Liszt, Slovak Institutes, and Czech Centres emphasize the ongoing significance of national identity in the field of cultural diplomacy and the difficulties in promoting a nation's brand in a globalized context. These findings are in line with the idea that national identity remains a crucial element in cultural diplomacy and National Cultural Institutes. The directors' experiences illustrate the complexities of promoting national culture, the necessity for adaptive strategies, and the importance of both historical and contemporary cultural elements for successful cultural diplomacy. These insights provide a deeper understanding of how cultural policies can be effectively designed to enhance national identity and cultural diplomacy in

European Union member states. The findings underscore the need for an urgent and broader discussion of cultural policy in the context of national identity, particularly in post-socialist countries like Slovakia.

This discussion is vital for developing comprehensive and strategically effective cultural diplomacy strategies that appeal to diverse audiences in an increasingly globalised world. The results of our analysis offer a sophisticated understanding of Slovak national identity, emphasizing its profound foundation in cultural legacy, family history, and personal values. Although numerous individuals exhibit pride and a strong sense of attachment, others are confronted with ambivalence or uncertainty about the future. These observations underscore the significance of crafting cultural diplomacy strategies that accentuate the exceptional traditions, customs, and historical narratives that characterize Slovak identity. Additionally, it is vital to strengthen ties with the Slovak diaspora through cultural initiatives and community support; engage in political issues that impact national identity; promote transparency, good governance, and progressive policies; and cultivate a form of national pride that is inclusive and open to global integration. By addressing these aspects, cultural policymakers can help preserve and promote Slovak national identity in a way that connects present and future generations, ensuring that Slovak identity remains a source of pride and unity in an increasingly globalized world.

Slovakia's nation branding efforts, exemplified by the "Good Idea Slovakia" campaign, reflect both the potential and the pitfalls of nation branding. By learning from the insights of experts and practitioners like Simon Anholt, Andrej Kona, Petra Steiger, Zuzana Palovic, and Zulf Hyatt-Khan, and addressing the identified challenges, Slovakia can develop a more effective and inclusive branding strategy that genuinely reflects its national identity and aspirations. The integration of cultural diplomacy, genuine public engagement, and addressing regional disparities will be essential in creating a sustainable and authentic national brand.

The role of cultural diplomacy in nation branding is pivotal. Effective cultural diplomacy involves engaging foreign audiences through cultural exchange and mutual understanding, rather than merely promoting a country's assets. Anholt (2024) highlights the British Council's model of mutuality, where cultural diplomacy is about sharing and co-creating cultural experiences with other countries. This approach fosters genuine connections and enhances a country's reputation more sustainably.

In our efforts to build a national brand in Slovakia, we have identified several challenges based on the data we have collected:

Lack of Public Engagement: The branding initiatives often do not resonate with the general public, leading to a lack of ownership and identification with the brand (Anholt, 2024; Kona, 2018; Steiger, 2021; Palovic, 2024).

Overemphasis on Visual Identity: There is a tendency to focus on logos and slogans rather than substantive actions that build the nation's reputation (Anholt, 2024; Kona, 2018).

Elite-Driven Processes: The development of the nation brand has been predominantly driven by the elite, with limited input from the broader population, which can undermine the authenticity and effectiveness of the brand (Anholt, 2024; Kona, 2018; Steiger, 2021; Palovic, 2024).

Historical and Regional Disparities: Slovakia's complex history and regional inequalities pose significant challenges to creating a unified national identity and brand (Anholt, 2024; Kona, 2018; Steiger, 2021; Palovic, 2024).

Media Influence and Political Control: Politicians and the opposition play significant roles in shaping the country's brand. Media narratives, often dominated by a liberal perspective, heavily influence the country's image. This raises questions about the actual control a government has over its brand image, especially if it does not align with popular geopolitical trends (Steiger, 2021).

Criticism of Elitism: The "Good Idea Slovakia" brand has faced criticism for its perceived elitism and exclusion of the general populace. While the brand addresses a "native" audience, it seldom features ordinary Slovak people, instead highlighting collective achievements and modern symbols like successful startups and innovative thinking (Steiger, 2021).

Lack of Authentic Public Identification: According to Zuzana Palovic (2024), successful country branding must resonate with the population on a deeper level. The branding needs to speak to the soul of the people and not just look good on promotional materials. Without this authentic connection, the brand is unlikely to effectively communicate Slovakia's identity to the outside world.

Underfunding of Cultural Diplomacy: Zulf Hyatt-Khan (2024) points out that cultural diplomacy is often neglected and underfunded, which limits the potential of Slovakia's nation brand. There is a need for greater investment in cultural initiatives that can showcase Slovakia's rich heritage and contemporary cultural achievements.

Recommendations for Future Branding Strategies of the Slovak Republic

To address these challenges, Slovakia's nation branding efforts should consider the following recommendations:

Inclusive Branding Processes: Engage a broader cross-section of society in the branding process to ensure that the brand resonates with and is owned by the public (Kona, 2018; Steiger, 2021; Palovic, 2024).

Focus on Actions Over Symbols: Prioritize real, impactful actions that enhance the country's reputation over the creation of visual symbols and marketing slogans (Anholt, 2024; Kona, 2018).

Promote Cultural Exchange: Emphasize cultural relations and mutual cultural exchange to build genuine connections and enhance Slovakia's image abroad (Anholt, 2024; Kona, 2018).

Address Regional Disparities: Recognize and address regional disparities within Slovakia to create a more cohesive and representative national brand (Anholt, 2024; Kona, 2018; Steiger, 2021; Palovic, 2024).

Broaden Public Debate: Ensure a comprehensive and inclusive communication strategy that reflects the diversity of Slovakia, incorporating feedback from professional and public debates (Steiger, 2021).

Integration with Diaspora: Better integrate the efforts of Slovak public and Slovak artists abroad with those within Slovakia to leverage the full potential of cultural diplomacy and representation (Kona, 2018, Palovic 2024).

Invest in Cultural Diplomacy: Increase funding for cultural diplomacy initiatives to better showcase Slovakia's cultural assets and enhance its international reputation. This includes supporting cultural centres, arts, and heritage projects that can tell compelling stories about Slovakia's history and contemporary achievements (Hyatt-Khan, 2024).

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